

FEATURES OF THE PRESENTATION OF THE SYMBOLIC MEANING OF COLLOQUIALISMS WITH THE COMPONENT “FRUIT” IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A DICTIONARY INTERPRETATION

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Abstract: The article studies the features of symbolic meaning in colloquialisms formed from the names of widely known, rare fruits and hybrid fruits. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of linguistic and extralinguistic factors influencing the formation of hidden meaning.

Keywords: symbolic meaning, colloquialisms, colloquial expressions, non-standardized vocabulary, decoding hidden meaning.

At present, the problem of studying the hidden meaning of individual thematic groups of colloquial English vocabulary is acquiring great importance in linguistic science due to the identification of new meanings, transformations of semantics in view of social and economic changes, and the withdrawal of individual colloquialisms from the active dictionary due to the loss of productivity and necessity.

The main problems include the following: a) studying colloquial language in terms of lexicographic analysis online [4, 540] and printed dictionary sources [1, 10; 3, 128]; b) identifying new colloquialisms based on fiction, newspaper and dictionary texts [5, 70; 6, 88]; c) analyzing coded vocabulary by revealing meaning [2, 192; 7.19]; d) studying colloquial language through modern trends in linguistics [8, 23; 9, 202].

The relevance of compiling a new type of dictionary definition as part of thematic lexicographic sources lies in the current widespread interest in the development and study of the problem of the theoretical foundation of colloquial speech, the study of colloquial language as an integral system, and insufficient developments in terms of studying homonymy, polysemy, synonymy, and antonymy of colloquialisms in modern English studies.

Colloquialisms with hidden meaning of fruits in the presence of a number of names can form colloquial meanings in all names, or in part of them. The acquisition of colloquial meaning depends on the degree of spread of use of a particular name.

Thus, names that have a wider scope of use in colloquial speech are subject to a higher percentage of probability of the emergence of a colloquial meaning, in contrast to terminological concepts known mainly only to a closed professional group of people.

Let's compare the interpretation of a colloquial noun derived from the name of a fruit in the crowdsourced dictionary Urban Dictionary Online:

a) *annona* in the meaning of “a young woman, a girl with very expressive eyes, but hair that is off-putting in appearance (hair is disheveled, like a cave monster). When she wakes up, the girl becomes angry and hungry. She has a lot of male friends, loves board games and sleep. The girl is a fibber and a liar. However, her pleasant appearance allows all her mistakes to be forgiven.”
Cp.:

Girl: Hey! Look over there, it's a wild annona.

Boy: Hair like a cave monster, but the most beautiful eyes [11].

b) *soursop* “a period of time when a person is angry because his lie/fiction has been exposed.” For instance: “Don’t be such a soursop, Michelle” [11].

c) *wild guanabana* “going on an exciting journey that can change an ordinary life.”

Mike: Bro, have you been on a Wild Guanabana yet?

Steve: No, but I sure need too! [11].

Colloquial words and expressions were also formed from variants of the names of the *annona* fruit, namely: *soursop*, *guanabana*. In the above examples, although the names of the same fruit are used, the implicit meanings denote completely different concepts. However, *graviola* did not form such colloquial semantics, which is due to the less frequent use of this name in everyday communication.

Colloquialisms formed on the basis of well-known fruits are subject to polysemy. Thus, *apple* as a colloquial noun has 6 meanings at once: “1. a person (as used in American English) (often noted with the joint use of such adjectives as: *bad*, *rotten*); 2. stupid (about a person), a victim of fraud; 3. a person inexperienced in terms of material excesses; 4. a head; 5. an important person (corresponds to both American and Australian English). 6. a person who does not use drugs” [10]. As can be seen from the above examples, the meaning of the component “person” is subject to narrowing and specification in terms of characterizing intellectual abilities, position in society, etc.

Thus, by conducting such an analysis, it is possible to note the possibility of creating not only projects of thematic dictionaries, but also lexicographic sources aimed at systematizing colloquial homonyms, synonyms, antonyms and polysemantic words. Systematization of such vocabulary is necessary to eliminate inaccuracies in understanding the contextual meaning.

Of course, dictionaries of colloquial and non-standardized vocabulary have a dual parameter in the selection of vocabulary. Therefore, when establishing a more accurate picture, it is necessary to search for lexemes in several dictionary sources in order to avoid a subjective approach in statistical calculations.

When compiling a dictionary entry of a new type, it is important that the headwords are given in alphabetical order for the convenience of searching for a colloquialism.

In the case of a variant or several alternative variants of a colloquialism, the words should be placed in parentheses with the note “variant” and also highlighted in bold, italics.

A direct translation should be presented in parentheses, which helps to identify parallels between the direct and metaphorical meaning based on associations, hidden symbolic meaning. After the headword, stylistic, grammatical, derivational and other notes should be placed (for example, noun, verb, plural, abbreviated, etc.).

After the notes, an explanation is given. A short definition may contain an equivalent translation of the word into Russian, the closest synonym, or a definition in the absence of an equivalent.

An expanded definition may include additional information (for example, features of word-formation models, extralinguistic data on cultural studies, territorial features of distribution, etc.).

After the dictionary definition, a number of examples of the use of colloquialisms, slangisms in various types of contexts should be presented to identify the features of situational use. Most dictionary entries should be provided with examples in the form of dialogues, instant messenger correspondence, online dictionaries or excerpts from modern fiction for the most complete presentation of the meaning of colloquial words and expressions in modern discourse.

Decoding the hidden meaning is easily predicted from colloquialisms with the component “fruit”, which served as the productive basis for other parts of speech by means of the suffixal method of formation.

Ср. colloquial verb and noun: *apple knock* “to behave ingenuously like a country bumpkin” and *apple-knocker* “1. a rural, unsophisticated person. 2. a person engaged in apple picking. 3. a fool”. In both colloquialisms, the main component in the meaning is the element “country” as simple, unsophisticated.

Thus, in connection with the emergence of a large number of colloquial words and expressions with the component “fruit” with hidden semantics, it is important to compile dictionary definitions, including information describing individual characteristics (color, taste, smell, etc.). Combining information of a linguistic and extralinguistic nature, it becomes possible to reveal associative parallels between the primary meaning and the new colloquial meaning using the comparative-contrastive method.

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